

ADAPTATION AND ACTIVE INTERACTION OF YOUNG CHILDREN WITH ENVIRONMENT

¹Sharipova Dilbar Gulamovna, ²Hikmatova Dilrabo Pulatovna, ³Safarova Zakiya Teshayevna

^{1,2}Lecturers at the Faculty of Philology, Bukhara State University

³Lecturer at the Department of Zoology and General Biology of Bukhara State University

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Abstract. *The article presents data on adaptation and active interaction of children with an early age environment, describes their adaptive capabilities, biological activity cannot provide a modern child with optimal interaction with the environment, since it naturally drops sharply in conditions of high comfort.*

Keywords: *society, child, genetics, innate programs, thermoregulation, physiological phenomena, vocalization, reflexes, brain, biological activity.*

Introduction. A child is born as a biological being possessing the structural and physiological features of the human brain, in which the hereditary genetic program of behavior is minimized, although almost all sensory channels are ready to function. Some of the innate behavior programs are built according to the constants of the prehistoric period of human development and in changing modern conditions, they do not carry out a genuine adaptive function (thermoregulation, the so-called rudimentary reflexes).

Results and discussion. Other unconditionally reflex acts (vocalization, expressive movements) are specifically focused on the instincts of motherhood, but at the human level they can also be realized through the social motivation of parents' behavior. Biological activity in the earliest period of postnatal ontogenesis is associated with the struggle for energy. But the living conditions of children in modern society are such that the satisfaction of children's energy needs is often carried out with a certain anticipation.

This eliminates the very possibility of a long-term manifestation of activity, which, with a shortage of food, oxygen, and temperature, would be supported by the corresponding dominants. Thus, biological activity cannot provide a modern child with optimal interaction with the environment, since the temperature naturally drops sharply in conditions of high comfort. In addition, the system of biological connections with the outside world is characterized by a certain cyclicity, due to the period between the satisfaction of organic needs and its subsequent restoration. The biological activity of the child unfolds within two types. The first is a reaction to external influences (defensive and defensive) and the second is a "reaction" to the absence of an irritant (food, etc.).

This second type of activity would be correctly called not a "reaction", but an "action". A fundamentally different function of activity is psychological-partly related to the phenotypic superstructure over the biological foundation, but mainly it is built in the process of the child's interaction with the environment, having as a physiological component -indicative reactions that occupy an important place in the structure of any kind of sensory or objective activity. Social experimental studies have shown that complex interanalytical connections are formed on the basis of indicative reactions, thanks to which signals of different modalities can acquire sign meaning in relation to each other. So, the sound can become a signal of light, or a static or moving image.

Here, therefore, in some initial forms, the fact that H.S. is overcome is overcome. Vygotsky called signaling, passively reflecting natural connections. A situation in which one signal serves as a sign of another signal contains an idea of some initial forms of distraction. On the basis of interanalysatory orientation links, a functional system is formed that can be in a state of activation for a long time. This happens provided that the integrity of the stimulus system through which these connections were formed is violated. Experimental data show that the indicative activity is caused by the mechanisms of expectation, search or achievement of the result of an action in sensory or objective activity, while there is a developed indicative activity of a critical level of "saturation", which is significantly higher than when satisfying organic needs.

Conclusions. The data show that the level of indicative activity, at least within the sensory sphere, initially depends on the stage at which, after birth, the "unification" of various analyzers begins (through external stimulation) into a single functional system.

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